

Using Logistic Regression to Predict the Direction of Nigeria Stock Market Returns (Based on some Selected Sector Indexes, 2015-2022)

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Abstract:

The direction of the Nigeria Stock performance based on some selected sector indexes was considered, with data of weekly Nigeria Exchange Limited (NGX) indexes (which included closing prices of the NGX All Share Index, Banking, Oil and Gas, Insurance, Consumer Goods and Top 30 Companies for the period, 5th January, 2015 to 31st October, 2022. After transforming the original series to returns, the data were analyzed using correlation analysis and multiple logistic regression analysis. The correlation analysis was carried out to examine the correlations between the NGX ASI returns and each of the selected sector indexes returns, and the result

showed that NSE ASI returns were correlated with all the selected sector indexes returns; although Oil and Gas and Insurance showed weak correlations. Logistic regression was used to model the dependent variable, direction (either upward or downward) of NGX ASI returns and independent variables (which are Banking, Oil and Gas, Insurance, Consumer Goods and Top 30 Companies), sector indexes returns of NGX. The findings showed that NGX Banking, Consumer Goods and Top 30 Companies returns contributed significantly to the prediction of the dependent variable, the direction of NGX ASI returns; while Oil and Gas and Insurance were not significant. It was concluded that although the NGX ASI returns were correlated with the five selected sector indexes returns used in this study, only three sectors (Banking, Consumer Goods and NGX 30) were good enough to be used in predicting the direction of the Nigeria Stock Market returns with the overall accuracy of about 70.17 percent. Thus, logistic regression model could be used by investors (individuals or institutions) to enhance their ability to predict the upward or downward direction of NGX ASI.

Keywords: NGX ASI, Logistic regression, Correlation, Sector index returns, Binary variable, Accuracy.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 62M10

Introduction

Stock market is an economic institution which promotes efficiency in capital formation and

allocation, and enables governments and industries to raise long-term capitals for financing new projects and expanding and modernizing industrial and commercial

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concerns. Stock market is a common feature of a modern economy, and it is reputed to perform functions that promote the growth and development of the economy (see, Iornav, 2015). Stock markets are usually divided into sectors by industry classification. Stock market sectors information allows investors and scholars to observe the performance of a particular stock in relation to other stocks and/or stock index (see Emenike, 2017).

Analysing the performance of stock market sectors will reveal the nature of interaction between the sector, which will in turn form the basis for portfolio selection and investment decisions. Stock market sector analysis also provides the basis for benchmarking the performance of a particular stock or sector, as well as a guide to domestic and international diversification of investments.

Each of the sectors or combination of sectors in a stock market has an index which reflects the general sector(s) movement. A stock index or stock market index is a measurement of the value of a section of the stock market. It is computed from the prices of selected stocks (typically a weighted average). According to Guha et al. (2016), stock market index is considered as a barometer to judge the sentiment of the market. The index is usually monitored by different stock market stakeholders, such as financial markets researchers and analysts for providing accurate analysis, investors to purchase or sell financial assets, policy makers for future policy formulation, and so on.

According to Iornav (2015), stock market indices are used as a general measure of the performance of stock markets in terms of price appreciation or depreciation. Sharabati (2013) asserts that these indices are important economic indicators, as they gauge the health and, very often, can predict the future direction of economic activity. Confirming that local and international investors follow an exchange's All Share Index (ASI) closely and takes a cue on the economy from how the equity market behaves. The index affects the overall confidence in all sectors of the economy.

According to Mingyue and YuSong (2016), the direction of the stock market index refers to the movement of the price index or the trend of fluctuation in the stock market index in the future. Predicting the direction is a practical issue that heavily influences a financial traders' decision to buy or sell an instrument. Accurate forecast of the trends of the stock index can help investors to acquire opportunities for gaining profit in the stock exchange. Hence, precise forecasting of the trends of the stock price index can be extremely advantageous for investors (Gholamiagonabadi et al., 2014). Leung et al. (2000) hold the view that trading could be made profitable by an accurate prediction of the direction of movement of the stock index. Their work suggested that financial forecasters and traders should focus on accurately predicting the direction of movement so as to minimize the estimates deviations from the actual observed values. According to Mostafa (2010), accurate predictions of the direction of stock price indices are very important for investor. These days, stock market has become an attractive way to generate returns and investors or traders with a goal to earn quick money enters into the market, but to be successful, timing of the entry and exist in the stock is very important (Rohit et al., 2021).

The Nigeria Exchange (NGX) Group, formally known as the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) dates its history back to 15th September, 1960, when the Lagos Stock Exchange was founded. In 2021, the NSE was fully demutualized from a member-owned not-for-profit entity into a shareholder-owned, profit making entity, which gave rise to a new structure - Nigeria Exchange Group Plc. with subsidiaries – Nigeria Exchange Limited (NGX Exchange), NGX Regulation Limited (NGX REGCO), and NGX Real Estate Limited (NGX RELCO). The NSE has a broad index known as the ASI, which measures the overall stock market performance, while other sector indexes are used to gauge the sectorial performance and efficiency of the stock market. These include; the Top 30 Companies (NGX 30), NGX Banking, NGX Consumer Goods (formerly, Foods and Beverages), NGX Insurance, NGX Oil and Gas and so on.

Statement of Problem

Low return on investment had been identified as a big problem for investors. There are cases where investments of over five years yielded well below the expected returns, and this kind of situation had discouraged a lot of local and international investors. Some of these investors have also lost thousands and millions of their country's currency in the cause of investing in the stock market. Analysing the performance of stock market sectors in Nigeria will reveal the nature of interaction among sectors of the Nigerian stock market, which will in turn form the basis for portfolio selection, trading strategy and investment decisions for stock experts and investors. Thus, this paper seeks to predict the direction of the Nigeria All Share Index from 2015 to 2022.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to predict the direction of the NGX ASI returns for the period, 5th January, 2015 to 31st October, 2022, using some selected NGX sector indexes (which include Banking, Consumer Goods, Oil & Gas, Insurance and Top 30 Companies), which will in turn form the basis for portfolio selection, trading strategy and investment decisions for stock experts and investors. Specifically, the objectives of this study are;

- to determine the long-term movement of the NGX ASI price returns and some of the selected sector indexes (namely; Banking, Consumer Goods, Oil & Gas, Insurance and Top 30 Companies) for the period under study;
- to examine the correlation between NGX ASI price returns and each of the selected sector indexes for the period under study;
- to establish the relationship that exists among the direction of the NGX ASI price returns and the selected sector indexes for the period under study;
- to determine the contributions of the selected sector indexes to the direction of the NGX ASI price returns for the period under study; and
- to evaluate the predictive power of the established model using coefficient of

determination, accuracy, sensitivity and specificity.

Literature Review

Sharabati (2013) investigated the relationship between Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) market development and Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP). The daily data on ASE sectors (Banks, Insurances, Services and Industries sectors) and GDP, collected from ASE market data base and government institutions data base for the period, 29 December 1999 to 30 December 2012 were analyzed using statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics, t-test, ANOVA test, correlation, simple and multiple regressions, stepwise regression. The results showed that the finance sectors had the highest effect on ASE market performance, followed by the industrial sector, then the services sector. They concluded that fluctuations of prices in one stock index could be determined or predicted to some extent using a part of the information set provided by the other stock indices.

Nagendra and Haritha (2014) investigated the correlation between the prime index on the National Stock Exchange (NSE) of India Ltd (Nifty) returns and other sectorial Indexes returns. The data on NSE Nifty and seven NSE Sectorial Indexes (Auto, Bank, Energy, FMCG, IT, Metal, and Pharma) for the period, (2006 - 2010) were analyzed using correlation analysis to find the correlation between NSE Nifty monthly returns and Sectorial Indexes monthly returns. The results showed that NSE NIFTY monthly average returns for diverse periods were correlated with most of the sector indexes returns. It was concluded that NSE NIFTY influenced the performance of sector indexes performance to identify the risk factor difference across the risk of sector indexes and NSE Nifty Index.

Michael and Bankole (2021) investigated the relationship between the returns of the sectoral indices of the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) for the period, 4th October, 2013 to 30th September, 2016. The sectoral indices for this study included weekly values of Banking,

Insurance, Consumer Goods, Oil & Gas, Industrial, NSE (30) index, and all share index and were gotten from Meristem Security Limited. The data were analysed using correlations analysis on. The result showed that returns across various sectors correlated which indicated that risk diversification would be difficult. It was concluded that All Share Index returns had a positive relationship with the vast majority of the sectoral indices indicating that many indexes performances were alongside the “All-share index”.

Ali et al. (2018) applied logistic regression model to predict stock performance of Pakistan’s Stock Exchange (PSX). Different financial and accounting ratios (sales growth, debt to equity ratio, book to price ratio, earning per share, return on equity and current ratio) were used as independent variables and stock performance (either “good” or “poor”) as dependent variable for the period, (2011-2015). The result showed that financial and accounting ratios significantly predicted the stock performance. The findings indicated that their prediction was about 89.77 percent accurate for prediction of good as well as bad performance of stock. It was concluded that the six firm specific accounting and financial ratios were good enough to predict stock performance. Also, that logistic regression model could be used by investors, individual as well as institutions or fund managers to enhance their ability to predict “good” or “poor” stock.

Dedu and Saforo (2016) examined the efficacy of financial ratios as predictors of stock performances of 20 randomly selected companies listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange Composite Index (GSE-CI) for the period, (2011-2013). The data were primarily collected from the Ghana Stock Exchange website (www.gse.gov.gh) and from the annual financial statements of the 20 companies, and were analyzed using binary logistic regression. The study showed that using financial ratios, companies’ annual performance on the GSE-CI could be predicted with a 70 percent level of accuracy into two categories (either “good” or “poor”) based on whether or not that particular company outperformed the GSE-CI. It was concluded that the model developed could

enhance the stock performance forecasting ability of investors.

Jose et al. (2020) studied the performance of logistics regression model in different conditions under multivariate normality. A Monte Carlo simulation study was done in which artificial datasets were generated by employing the latent variable approach, under different variance-covariance matrices, varying sample sizes and prevalence. For each of the combinations, 1000 simulations were carried out. Logistic regression was performed and compared to Probit Regression using Parameter estimate, likelihood ratio test, null and residual deviances, different pseudo R squared measures, AIC and BIC and efficiency of the models. It was evident from AIC and BIC values that Logit and Probit models fitted the dataset equally well in all combination of sample sizes, correlation structure and proportion of outcome, but sensitivity and specificity values showed that Logit models predicted the outcome better than Probit in most of the situations.

Eke (2016) examined the statistical modeling of monthly returns from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) using probability distributions (normal and logistic distributions) for the period, (1995 -2014). The monthly data on NSE were collated from the Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria, 2015 Edition and were analyzed to determine the returns from the stock exchange, its means and standard deviation in order to obtain the best suitable distribution. Furthermore, comparative analysis was done between the logistic and normal distribution. The findings proved that the logistic distribution was better than the normal distribution in modeling returns from the NSE due to its P-Value being great than the 5% level of significance and also because of its minimum variance.

Methodology

Data

The data used for this study, as presented in Table 1 (see Appendix 1), consist of weekly closing prices of some NGX All Share Index and

some selected sector indexes for the period of 8 years (5th January, 2015 to 31st October, 2022). The selected sector indexes include Banking, Insurance, Consumer Goods, oil & gas and Top 30 Companies (NGX 30). The study is limited to the data on the Nigeria Stock Market downloaded from the global financial website (<http://m.ng.Investing.com>) and also to the method(s) of analysis that will be employed on the data.

Method of Analysis

Apart from the descriptive analysis, which included the use of graphical representations to show the long term movement of stock indexes under the period of study, correlation analysis and multiple logistic regression were also employed in this study.

The Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis will be carried out to measure the degree of association or relationship that exists between two or among more than two variables, as well as testing the significance or otherwise of the degree of the association. The correlation coefficient will be obtained using the software, R, while the test for the significance of the coefficient will be conducted as described in Nwobi (2003). The test statistic to test the null hypothesis ($H_0 : \rho = 0$) could be either of the followings;

(i) the Student's t-test statistic (when the number of pairs, n , of X_i and Y_i is small; that is, $n < 30$), given by,

$$t = r_{ij} \left(\frac{1 - r_{ij}^2}{n - 2} \right)^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

(with the critical value, $t_{\alpha; n-2}$, for a one-tailed test; or $t_{\alpha/2; n-2}$, for a two-tailed test)

(ii) the Z-test statistic (when the number of pairs, n , of X_i and Y_i is large; that is, $n \geq 30$, and the joint distribution of X_i and Y_i is bivariate normal), given by,

$$Z = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1 + r_{ij}}{1 - r_{ij}} \right) (n - 3)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

(with the critical value, Z_{α} , for a one-tailed test; or $Z_{\alpha/2}$, for a two-tailed test)

Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression (LR) is usually used to explore the relationship between a categorical dependent variable and at least one independent variable. The idea behind LR is to model a categorical variable that is binary (or has more than two possible values) using independent variables that are continuous, discrete, or a mix of these two (see, for example, King, 2008; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). For a binary dependent variable ($Y = 0, 1$), the method of LR can be derived from the linear regression model by considering the effects of the dependent variable being binary (Kutner et al, 2005).

According to Gujarati (2004), LR model looks non-linear in the parameters, but with a suitable mathematical transformation, it can be made linear in the parameters. Thus, LR model is intrinsically linear. In situations when the dependent variable, Y , is binary; that is,

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if success is recorded} \\ 0, & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

the interest will be centered on $P_r(Y = 1/x)$, which is usually denoted by $\pi(x)$. According to Hosmer and Lemeshow (2000), the LR model is given by,

$$\pi(x) = P_r(Y = 1/x) = \frac{e^u}{1 + e^u} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-u}} \quad (4)$$

where,

$$u = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x \quad (5)$$

for a simple LR (in which the interest is in one independent variable). In the multiple LR case, having $x_j; j = 0, 1, \dots, k$, (5) will be rewritten as,

$$u = x_i \beta \quad (6)$$

such that the conditional probability of success given x values, $\pi(x)$ is given by,

$$\pi(x_i) = P_r(y_i = 1/x) = \frac{e^{x_i \beta}}{1 + e^{x_i \beta}} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x_i \beta}} \quad (7)$$

and the probability of failure is given by,

$$1 - \pi(x_i) = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x_i \beta}} = \frac{e^{-x_i \beta}}{1 + e^{-x_i \beta}} \quad (8)$$

According to Nwobi and Ohaegbulem (2013), the central mathematical concept that underlies LR is the natural logarithm of the odds for success (otherwise called logit). The odds are defined as the ratio of the probability of the occurrence of an event to the probability of non-occurrence of that same event. Using the probability probability of success in (7), the odds are given as,

$$Odds = \frac{\pi(x_i)}{1 + \pi(x_i)} = \frac{\frac{1}{1 + e^{-x_i \beta}}}{\frac{e^{-x_i \beta}}{1 + e^{-x_i \beta}}} = \frac{1}{e^{-x_i \beta}} = e^{x_i \beta} \quad (9)$$

$$L(\beta) = f(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n / \beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n \binom{n_i}{y_i} \pi(x_i)^{y_i} (1 - \pi(x_i))^{n_i - y_i} \quad (11)$$

The odds varies from 0 to ∞ , and when $\pi(x_i) = 0.5$; the odds are 1. Based on (7), the relationship between the probability of Y and X is nonlinear; and for that reason, the natural log transformation of the odds is necessary to make the relationship between the binary dependent variable and independent variables linear. To obtain the standard formulation of LR, known as logit (which is also referred to as the LR model), the natural logarithm of (7) is taken. That is,

$$Logit[\pi(x_i)] = \ln \left[\frac{\pi(x_i)}{1 + \pi(x_i)} \right] = \ln(e^{x_i \beta}) = x_i \beta \quad (10)$$

where,

$\pi(x_i)$ is the probability of a 1 (the proportion of 1's, the mean of Y), and e is a mathematical constant called Euler's number, which is approximately equal to 2.78, and β is a vector of parameters to be estimated. The logit takes values from $-\infty$ (very low odds) to $+\infty$ (very high odds). A logit of zero correspond to odd of one, and to probability, $\pi(x_i) = 0.5$.

The Maximum Likelihood (ML) method will be used to estimate the LR model parameters. The method estimates the parameter, β , by maximizing the likelihood function provided that the data follow a certain distribution. Since y_i follows a Binomial distribution, then the joint probability density function (pdf) of y_i is,

where,

$\pi(x_i)^{y_i}$ is the probability of y_i success; $(1-\pi(x_i))^{n_i-y_i}$ is the probability of n_i-y_i failures; and $\binom{n_i}{y_i}$ is a constant term in the likelihood function. Furthermore, maximizing $L(\beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n \pi(x_i)^{y_i} (1-\pi(x_i))^{n_i-y_i}$ gives the same result as maximizing (11), since $\binom{n_i}{y_i}$ does

not contain $\pi(x_i)$. When $n_i = 1$ and $y_i = 0$ or 1 , $\binom{n_i}{y_i} = 1$. Therefore, (11) becomes,

$$L(\beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n \pi(x_i)^{y_i} (1-\pi(x_i))^{n_i-y_i} \quad (12)$$

The corresponding log likelihood function of (12) is given as,

$$l(\beta) = \ln L(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \{y_i \ln[\pi(x_i)] + (1-y_i) \ln[1-\pi(x_i)]\} \quad (13)$$

Differentiating (13) partially w.r.t β and equating to zero gives,

$$\frac{\partial \ln L(\beta)}{\partial \beta} = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - \pi(x_i)] x_{ij} = 0 \quad (14)$$

Equations (14) are nonlinear in β and hence the estimates are obtained by numerical methods (see, for example, Kutner et al., 2005). According to Maxwell and Nwali (2018), (14) can be solved using Newton-Raphson techniques to obtain the maximum likelihood estimates for the β . The Newton-Raphson equation for iteration is defined as,

$$\beta^{(i+1)} = \beta^{(i)} + (X'VX)^{-1} X'(Y - \mu_Y) \quad (15)$$

where,

μ_Y is an $(n \times 1)$ column vector of the probabilities of success, given by,

$$\mu_Y = \begin{bmatrix} \pi(x_1) \\ \pi(x_2) \\ \vdots \\ \pi(x_n) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

V is an $(n \times n)$ diagonal matrix with elements, $\pi(x_i)[1-\pi(x_i)]$, Y , X and β 's and is given by,

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} \pi(x_1)[1-\pi(x_1)] & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \pi(x_2)[1-\pi(x_2)] & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \pi(x_n)[1-\pi(x_n)] \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

For the first step of the iteration, ($i = 0$), Newton-Raphson algorithm guesses the element of $\beta^{(i)}$ (that is, $\beta^{(0)}$) and uses the guess to find $\beta^{(i+1)}$ (that is, $\beta^{(1)}$). In the next iteration, ($i = 1$), the result for $\beta^{(i+1)}$ which is substituted for $\beta^{(1)}$ in (15) and then it solves for $\beta^{(i+1)}$ (that is, $\beta^{(2)}$). The iteration process continues until $\beta^{(i)} \approx \beta^{(i+1)}$. Note that at any step of the iteration, the elements of $\beta^{(i)}$ are used to solve for $\pi(x_i)$ which is further used for finding $(X'VX)^{-1}$ and $X'(Y - \mu_Y)$ at that step.

Goodness-of-Fit Test of Logistic Regression Model

The Likelihood Ratio Test (LRT) principle (see, John et al. 1984) shall be employed to test the joint hypothesis that all the coefficients except the intercept are zeros. Some other tests (see, for example, Hosmer and Lemeshow, 2000) can also be used to test for the model fit. A variant of the LRT referred to as the Omnibus test, tests the hypothesis that all the slopes are simultaneously equal to zero (see, Lawrence et al., 2006).

The test statistic for this goodness-of-fit is the likelihood ratio test statistic, given by,

$$G_0^2 = -2 \left[\ln L(\hat{b}_0) - \ln L(\hat{\beta}) \right] \sim \chi_{v, \alpha}^2 \quad (18)$$

where,

v is the degrees of freedom (such that, $v = k$), which is also the number of parameters in the model; $\ln L(\hat{\beta})$ is the log likelihood functions for the fitted model given in (13); and $\ln L(\hat{b}_0)$ is the log likelihood functions for the intercept model only. That is, $\pi(x_i)$ in (13) is defined as,

$$\pi(x_i) = \frac{e^{x_i b_0}}{1 + e^{x_i b_0}} \quad (19)$$

where,

b_0 is the intercept.

The decision rule for this goodness-of-fit test is to reject the null hypothesis if and only if the calculated test statistic, G_0^2 , is greater than or equal to the Chi-square critical value (that is, H_0 is to be rejected if and only if $G_0^2 \geq \chi_{v, \alpha}^2$)

The decision rule for this goodness-of-fit test would be such that if the null hypothesis was rejected, then the regression was of good fit to the dataset. Otherwise, it was not a good fit to the data set.

Best Model Selection Criteria

There are several criteria for selecting the best parsimonious model in LR of which Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) is well known. According to Akaike (1973), AIC is given by,

$$AIC = -2 \ln L(\hat{\beta}) + 2k \quad (20)$$

where,

k is the number of parameters in the model. According to Akaike (1973), the smaller the AIC, the better the model.

Coefficient of Multiple Determination for Logistic Regression Model

For the LR model, the coefficient of multiple determination, R^2 , which describes the proportion of variances of the dependent variable explained by the model shall be computed using Cox and Snell R^2 ; which is given as,

$$R_{CS}^2 = 1 - \exp \left[-\frac{2}{n} * l(\hat{\beta}) - l(\hat{b}_0) \right] \quad (21)$$

where,

$l(\hat{\beta})$ is the log likelihood functions for the fitted model given in (13) and $l(\hat{b}_0)$ is the log likelihood functions for the intercept model only; that is, $\pi(x_i)$ in (13) is given in (19). According to Nagerkerke (1991), (20) cannot reach 1. Thus, the adjusted version Nagerkerke R^2 is given by,

$$\bar{R}_N^2 = \frac{1 - \exp \left[-\frac{2}{n} * l(\hat{\beta}) - l(\hat{b}_0) \right]}{1 - \exp \left[2n^{-1} l(\hat{b}_0) \right]} \quad (22)$$

The Classification Table

The classification table gauges the predictive accuracy of a multivariate LR model. The method involves cross classifying the dependent variable with the categorical variable emanating from the fitted logistic probabilities, \hat{y} . According to Sharma (1996), the percentage of successes that have been correctly classified as success is called sensitivity of the model, whilst the percentage of failures that have been correctly classified is called specificity of the model. The failures that are incorrectly classified as success are referred to as false positive and the success that are incorrectly classified as failures are referred to as false negatives. A typical binary classification table is as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The Binary Classification Table of Observed and Predicted Outcomes for a Binary Response Model

		Predicted Outcome		Percent Correct
		$\hat{y} = 0$	$\hat{y} = 1$	
Observed Outcome	$y = 0$	n_{11}	n_{12}	$\frac{n_{11}}{n_{11} + n_{12}}(100)$
	$y = 1$	n_{21}	n_{22}	$\frac{n_{22}}{n_{21} + n_{22}}(100)$
Overall percentage				$\frac{n_{11} + n_{22}}{n_{11} + n_{12} + n_{21} + n_{22}}(100)$

Table 2 shows that the Overall Classification Accuracy of the model is $\frac{n_{11} + n_{22}}{n_{11} + n_{12} + n_{21} + n_{22}}(100)$; the Specificity of the model is $\frac{n_{11}}{n_{11} + n_{12}}(100)$; and the Sensitivity of the model is $\frac{n_{22}}{n_{21} + n_{22}}(100)$. Higher specificity and sensitivity are an indication of a good fit of the model (Hongwon, 2021).

Data Analyses

The graphical representation of the data on the selected NGX sector indexes for the period, 5th January, 2015 to 30th October, 2022 is presented in Figure 3 (see, Appendix 1). It showed that the long term movements of the selected NGX sector indexes have been fluctuating over the period under study. The plot of the NGX ASI, shown in Figure 3 shows a slightly upward trend which implies that there are some factors contributing to the fluctuation of the NGX ASI.

Therefore, an analysis will be conducted to ascertain those factors contributing to the movement of the NGX ASI. Thus, there is need

to establish a relationship that exists among direction of the NGX ASI and the selected NGX sector indexes.

Figure 1. Plots of the Weekly NGX ASI (5th January, 2015 to 30th October, 2022)

The Correlation between the Returns of NGX ASI Price and Each of the Selected Sector Indexes for the Period under Study

First and foremost, the selected NGX sector indexes are transformed to NGX sector indexes returns series by taking first difference of log series, given by

$$r_t = \ln(P_t) - \ln(P_{t-1}) \quad (23)$$

where,

r_t is a vector of the weekly returns of the NGX sectors indices; P_t is the closing value of sectors indices in week t ; and P_{t-1} is the previous week closing value of the sectors indices.

These NGX indexes returns are presented in Table 3 (see Appendix 1) and arranged in such a manner that ASI, Banking, Insurance, Consumer Goods, Oil & Gas and Top 30 Companies (NGX 30) returns are in Columns 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7, respectively. A binary variable was created as a function NGX ASI returns (that is, upward (coded 1), if the current weekly NGX ASI return was higher than the previous week NGX ASI returns and downward (coded 0), if otherwise) and arranged in Column 8.

Correlation analysis was conducted on the NGX indexes returns (ASI, Banking (BNKG), Insurance (INSU), Consumer Goods (CG) Oil & Gas (OG), and Top 30 Companies (NGX 30)) in order to determine the sector indexes that are related to NGX ASI.

Table 4. Correlation Matrix between “All Share Index” and Other Sector Indexes (Banking, Insurance, Consumer Goods, Oil and Gas and NGX 30) Returns of the Nigeria Exchange (NGX), for the period, 5th January 2015 to 30th October 2022

	All Share Index	NGX 30	Oil and Gas	Insurance	Banking	Consumer Goods
All Share Index	1	0.97	0.41	0.42	0.78	0.71
NGX 30		1	0.44	0.43	0.83	0.76
Oil and Gas			1	0.21	0.34	0.32
Insurance				1	0.39	0.34
Banking					1	0.56
Consumer Goods						1

The estimated population correlation, r_{ij} , are computed with the aid of a computer software, R , and the output is displayed in Table 4. Now, using (4), the followings are obtained for testing the correlation between NGX ASI returns and each of the selected sector indexes returns, namely; NGX 30, Banking, Consumer Goods, Oil & Gas and Insurance), respectively;

$$Z_{NGX\ 30} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1+0.97}{1-0.97} \right) (407-3)^{1/2} = 42.055;$$

$$Z_{BNKG} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1+0.78}{1-0.78} \right) (407-3)^{1/2} = 21.012;$$

$$Z_{CG} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1+0.71}{1-0.71} \right) (407-3)^{1/2} = 17.832;$$

$$Z_{OG} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1+0.41}{1-0.41} \right) (407-3)^{1/2} = 6.756; \text{ and}$$

$$Z_{INSU} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1+0.42}{1-0.42} \right) (407-3)^{1/2} = 6.998$$

The critical value for testing the population correlation, ρ , is given by

$$Z_{\alpha/2} = Z_{0.05/2} = Z_{0.025} = 1.960.$$

Since the calculated values of the Z-test statistic for the estimated population correlation, r_{ij} , between NGX ASI returns and each of the selected sector indexes returns (NGX 30,

BNKG, CG, OG and INSU) which are 42.055, 21.012, 17.832, 6.756, and 6.998, respectively) are greater than the critical value ($Z_{0.025} = 1.960$), the null hypotheses, H_0 's, of non-significance of the correlation coefficients are therefore rejected.

Thus, the NGX ASI returns and each of the selected sector indexes returns are significantly correlated.

Establishing the Relationship that Exists among the Direction of the NGX ASI Price Returns and the Selected Sector for the Period under Study.

Multiple logistic regression model was established among the dependent variable (which is the direction; either upward (coded 1) or downward (coded 0) and the independent variables (which are Banking, Insurance, Consumer Goods, Oil & Gas, and NGX 30 indexes returns) which are presented in Table 3 (see Appendix 1).

Table 5. Summary of the Fitted Logistic Regression Model

Term	Estimate	Std. Error	Statistic	p-Value
(Intercept)	-0.03	0.11	-0.28	0.78
NGX 30	-88.70	13.59	-6.53	0.00
Oil and Gas	2.97	3.76	0.79	0.43
Insurance	2.37	5.04	0.47	0.64
Banking	16.05	5.85	2.74	0.01
Consumer Goods	17.11	6.17	2.77	0.01

The multiple LR model are estimated with the aid of the computer software, *R*; and the results

output is displayed in Table 5. Thus, the estimated LR model becomes,

$$\text{Logit}[\hat{\pi}(x_i)] = -0.0318 - 88.7021(NGX\ 30) + 2.9655(OG) + 2.3722(INSU) + 16.0493(BNKG) + 17.1144(CG)$$

The Log likelihoods for LR Model is also computed with the aid of *R*; and the results output is as displayed in Table 6. Thus, the test

statistic for this goodness-of-fit of the LR model, as given in (18), becomes,

$$G_0^2 = -2[(-282.799) - (-225.332)] = 114.934$$

Table 6. Model Fit Statistics for the Fitted Logistic Regression

Log-Lik Intercept Only:	-282.110	Log-Lik Full Model:	-225.332
Deviance(401):	450.664	LR(5):	113.555
		Prob > LR:	0.000
McFadden's R2:	0.201	McFadden's Adj R2:	0.180
ML (Cox-Snell) R2:	0.243	Cragg-Uhler (Nagelkerke) R2:	0.325
McKelvey & Zavoina's R2:	0.437	Efron's R2:	0.245
Count R2:	0.720	Adj Count R2:	0.438
BIC:	486.717	AIC:	462.664

Given that the calculated value of the test statistic, $G_0^2 = 114.934$, is greater than the Chi-square critical value ($\chi_{5,0.05}^2 = 11.070$), the null hypothesis, H_0 , is therefore rejected. This implies that the LR model is of good fit to the data set.

It could be seen, from Table 5, that the estimated LR parameters for NGX 30, Banking and Consumer Goods are significant, with *p*-values, 0.00, 0.01, and 0.01, respectively; while the estimated LR parameters for Oil & Gas and Insurance are not significant, having gotten *p*-values, 0.43 and 0.64, respectively.

It is therefore concluded that the estimated LR parameters of the NGX 30, Banking and

Consumer Goods have significant relationships with the direction of NGX ASI returns, while those of Oil & Gas and Insurance have no significant relationships with the direction of NGX ASI returns.

Computations for the Reduced Logistic Regression Model

Given the development in the previous section, the estimated regression parameters $\hat{\beta}_2$ and $\hat{\beta}_3$ are removed from the list of parameters, and the LR process is done again to obtain the new (Reduced) LR model (see the results output in Table 7); which is expressed as,

$$\text{Logit}[\hat{\pi}(x_i)] = -0.0318 - 85.0791(NGX\ 30) + 15.6524(BNKG) + 16.8224(CG)$$

The goodness-of-fit test was also done for the reduced LR model (the results output is displayed in Table 6), the test statistic for this

goodness-of-fit of the LR model, as given in (18), becomes,

$$G_0^2 = -2[(-282.110) - (-225.784)] = 112.652$$

Given that the calculated value of the test statistic, $G_0^2 = 112.652$ is greater than the Chi-square critical value ($\chi_{3, 0.05}^2 = 7.815$), the null hypothesis, H_0 , is therefore rejected. This implies that the Reduced LR model is of good fit to the data set.

It could be seen, from Table 7, that the estimated Reduced LR parameters for NGX 30, Banking and Consumer Goods are significant with p -values, 0.00, 0.01, and 0.01, respectively. It is therefore concluded that the estimated LR parameters of NGX 30, Banking and Consumer Goods have significant relationships with the direction of NGX ASI returns.

Table 7. Summary of the Reduced Logistic Regression Model

Term	Estimate	Std. Error	Statistic	P-Value
(Intercept)	-0.03	0.11	-0.27	0.79
NGX 30	-85.08	12.87	-6.61	0.00
Banking	15.65	5.75	2.72	0.01
Consumer Goods	16.82	6.11	2.75	0.01

The Best Model Selection Criteria

With the Log likelihoods for LR model (computed with the aid of R) presented in Tables 6 and 8 for fitted and reduced models, respectively; and using (20), the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) for the fitted full model and fitted reduced model are, respectively, obtained as;

$$AIC_{fitted} = -2(-225.332) + 2(5) = 462.664$$

and

$$AIC_{reduced} = -2(-225.784) + 2(3) = 457.568$$

Thus, the best parsimonious estimated LR model becomes the reduced model,

$$\text{Logit}[\hat{\pi}(x_i)] = -0.0318 - 85.0791(\text{NGX } 30) + 15.6524(\text{BNKG}) + 16.8224(\text{CG})$$

The Contributions of the Sector Indexes to the Direction of the NGX ASI Price Returns for the Period under Study

The reduced logistic regression model showed that the NGX 30 had a negative significant relationship with the direction of NGX ASI returns. This implies that, $\exp(-85.079) = 0$. Thus, a unit increase in NGX 30, leads to a decrease in the odds of an increase (upward direction) of NGX ASI returns. Thus, a high value of NGX 30 is associated with a decrease (downward direction) of NGX ASI.

Banking had a positive significant relationship with the direction of NGX ASI returns. This

implies that, $\exp(15.6524) = 6,276,983$. Thus, a unit increase in Banking, leads to an increase in the odds of an increase (upward direction) of NGX ASI returns. Thus, a high value of Banking is associated with an increase (upward direction) of NGX ASI.

Also, Consumer Goods had a positive significant relationship with the direction of NGX ASI returns. This implies that, $\exp(16.8224) = 20,224,393$. Thus, a unit increase in Consumer Goods leads to an increase in the odds of an increase (upward direction) of NGX ASI returns. Thus, a high value of

Consumer Goods is associated with an increase (upward direction) of NGX ASI.

Evaluating the Predictive Power of the Logistic Regression Models

The coefficient of multiple determination, accuracy, sensitivity and specificity will be used to evaluate the predictive accuracy of the established models.

R² for the Fitted Full Logistic Regression Model

Log likelihoods for LR model is computed with the aid of R ; and the out is displayed in Table 6.

Using (21), Cox and Snell R^2 is computed as follows,

$$R_{CS}^2 = 1 - \exp \left\{ \left(\frac{-2}{407} \right) [(-225.332) - (-282.110)] \right\} = 0.243$$

And using (22), the adjusted version Nagerkerke R^2 is given by,

$$\bar{R}_N^2 = \frac{1 - \left\{ \left(\frac{-2}{407} \right) [(-225.332) - (-282.110)] \right\}}{1 - \exp [2(407^{-1})(-282.110)]} = 0.3246$$

Nagerkerke R^2 shows that about 32.46% of the variation in the dependent variable, $Y = 1$ (that is, the upward direction), is explained by the LR model. That is, about 32.46% of the total variation in the upward direction of the NGX ASI returns was accounted by variations in Banking, Insurance, Consumer Goods, Oil and Gas and NGX 30. This implies that about 67.54% of the total variation in the dependent variable, $Y = 1$ (that is, the upward direction) could be attributed to other factors affecting the direction of NGX ASI outside this model.

The Classification Table for the Fitted Logistic Regression Model

The classification table which indicates how well the model predicts cases to the two dependent variable categories displayed in Table 9. The specificity, which is the proportion of the correctly classified “downward direction” of the NGX ASI returns was 72.50% and the sensitivity which is the proportion of the correctly classified “up direction” of the NSE ASI returns was 71.50%. The accuracy which is the overall full model correct classification was 71.99%.

Table 8. Model Fit Statistics for the Reduced Logistic Regression

Log-Lik Intercept Only:	282.110	Log-Lik Full Model:	-225.784
Deviance(403):	451.568	LR(3):	112.651
		Prob > LR:	0.000
MCFadden's R2:	0.200	Mcfadden's Adj R2:	0.185
ML (Cox-Snell) R2:	0.242	Cragg-Uhler (Nagelkerke) R2:	0.322
McKelvey & Zavoina's R2:	0.432	Efron's R2:	0.243
Count R2:	0.705	Adj Count R2:	0.409
BIC:	475.603	AIC:	459.568

R² for the Reduced Logistic Regression Model

Log likelihoods for LR model is computed with the aid of R ; and the output is displayed in Table 8. Hence, using (21), Cox and Snell R^2 is computed as follows,

$$R_{CS}^2 = 1 - \exp\left\{\left(\frac{-2}{407}\right)[(-225.784) - (-282.110)]\right\} = 0.2418$$

And (22), the adjusted version Nagerkerke R^2 is given by,

$$\bar{R}_N^2 = \frac{1 - \left\{\left(\frac{-2}{407}\right)[(-225.784) - (-282.110)]\right\}}{1 - \exp\left[2(407^{-1})(-282.110)\right]} = 0.3224$$

Nagerkerke R^2 shows that about 32.24% of the variation in the dependent variable, $Y = 1$ (that is, the upward direction), is explained by the LR model. That is, about 32.24% of the total variation in the up direction of the NGX ASI returns was accounted by variations in NGX 30, Banking and Consumer Goods. This implies that about 67.76% of the total variation in the dependent variable, $Y = 1$ (that is, the upward direction) could be attributed to other factors affecting the direction of NGX ASI outside this model.

Table 9. Classification Table of Observed and Predicted Outcomes for the Fitted Logistic Regression Model

		Predicted Outcome		Percent Correct
		$\hat{y} = 0$	$\hat{y} = 1$	
Observed outcome	$y = 0$	145	55	72.5%
	$y = 1$	59	148	71.5%
Overall percentage				71.99%

Table 10. Classification Table of Observed and Predicted Outcomes for the Reduced Logistic Regression Model

		Predicted Outcome		Percent Correct
		$\hat{y} = 0$	$\hat{y} = 1$	
Observed outcome	$y = 0$	143	59	70.8%
	$y = 1$	61	144	70.24%
Overall percentage				70.52%

The Classification Table for the Reduced Logistic Regression Model

The classification table which indicates how well the model predicts cases to the two dependent variable categories displayed in Table 10. The specificity, which is the proportion of the

correctly classified “downward direction” of the NGX ASI returns was 70.79% and the sensitivity which is the proportion of the correctly classified “upward direction” of the NGX ASI returns was 70.79%. The accuracy which is the overall full model correct classification was 70.52%.

Summary

The study aimed at predicting the stock market performance using some selected sector indexes (Banking index, Consumer Goods index, Oil & Gas index, NGX 30 index, Insurance index). The correlation between NGX ASI price returns and each of the sector indexes was determined, as well as establishing the relationship that exists between the direction of the NGX ASI price returns and the selected sector indexes and assessing the contributions of the sector indexes to the direction of the NGX ASI price returns. The data used for this study were secondary weekly series downloaded from investing website (<http://m.ng.Investing.com>), for the period 05 January, 2015 to 31 October, 2022. The data on NGX index prices were transformed to index returns, and correlation analysis and multiple logistic regression were employed. The graphical representation of the stock indexes in Nigeria shows the long term movements of the Nigeria stock exchange indexes have been fluctuating over the years under study. Findings from the correlation analysis showed that correlations exist between NGX ASI returns and each of the selected sector indexes returns (which include NGX 30, Banking, Consumer Goods, Oil and Gas and Insurance). With regards to the correlation between “All Share Index” and other sectors indexes, the results showed that NGX 30 Index has the highest correlation with “All Share Index” at 0.97, followed by Banking and Consumer Goods Indexes with 0.78 and 0.71, respectively; while Insurance and Oil & Gas Indexes had least correlations with “All Share Index” at 0.42 and 0.41, respectively, which is in line with the findings of Micheal and Bankole (2021).

Logistic regression analysis was applied to investigate further the contributions of the selected sector indexes returns to the direction of ASI returns. The result of the goodness-of-fit test for the multiple LR model gave that the calculated test statistic (likelihood test), 114.934 was greater than the critical value, 11.070. It was concluded that the LR model was of good fit to the data set. The findings from this study led to the conclusion that the NGX 30, Banking and

Consumer Goods had significant relationships with the direction of NGX ASI return at 5% level of significance, while Oil and Gas and Insurance had no significant relationships with the direction of NGX ASI return.

Since the findings of the LR model showed that Oil & Gas and Insurance had no significant relationships with the direction of NGX ASI return, then Oil & Gas, and Insurance were removed from the LR model and it led to another re-run of the multiple LR analysis called the reduced LR model.

The results of the goodness-of-fit test for the Reduced LR model gave that the calculated value of the test statistic, 112.652 was greater than the critical value, 7.815. This was concluded that the LR model was of good fit to the data set. The findings from the Reduced LR model led to the conclusion that all the independent variables (which include, NGX 30, Banking, and Consumer Goods had significant relationships with the direction of NGX ASI return at 5% level of significance. A Nagerkerke R^2 for the Reduced LR model was obtained, which showed that about 32.24% of the total variations in the upward direction of NGX ASI return, was accounted by variations in Banking, Consumer Goods and NGX 30. This implies that about 67.77% of the variation could be attributed to other factors affecting the direction of NGX ASI return outside this reduced LR model.

The results of the predictive ability from the classification table of the Reduced LR model gave that the accuracy, which measures the overall percentage of correct classification made by the model was 70.52%, specificity, which is the percentage of the correctly classified “downward direction” of the NGX ASI return was 70.79% and the sensitivity, which is the percentage of the correctly classified “upward direction” of the NGX ASI returns was 70.24%.

The result of this work also showed that Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) for the full and Reduced LR model were 462.664 and 457.568, respectively; which implies the Reduced LR model was better than the LR model that included all five independent variables.

Conclusion

Findings of this study revealed that returns across various sectors tend to be positively correlated with the 'All Share Index' which indicated that risk diversification would be difficult.

The most important factors (sectors) associated with the direction NGX ASI returns include Top 30 Companies, Banking and Consumer Goods. NGX 30 had a negative significant relationship with the direction of NGX ASI returns. This implies that a unit increase in NGX 30 leads to a decrease in the odds of a decrease (downward direction) of NGX ASI returns. Banking had a positive significant relationship with the direction of NGX ASI returns. This implies that a unit increase in Banking leads to an increase in the odds of an increase (upward direction) of NGX ASI returns. Consumer Goods had a positive significant relationship with the direction of NGX ASI returns. This implies that a unit increase in Consumer Goods leads to an increase in the odds of an increase (upward direction) of NGX ASI returns.

Finally, Oil and Gas and Insurance were not statistically significant with the direction NGX ASI returns which indicated that contributions of Oil and Gas and Insurance were not important in predicting the direction of NGX ASI returns.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- (a) Stakeholders in the Nigeria financial industry are encouraged to look into Top 30 Companies, Banking and Consumer Goods in their formulation of policies.
- (b) Since the odds of an increase (upward direction) of NGX ASI returns is higher if there is a higher return on Banking and Consumer Goods, investors and traders are encouraged to choose Banking and Consumer Goods in developing effective market trading and investment strategies.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest, whatsoever, as far as this manuscript is concerned.

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Appendix 1

Table 1. Weekly Data of All Share Index and Some Sector Indexes of the Nigeria Exchange (NGX) for the Period 5th January, 2015 to 30th October, 2022

Date	All-Share-Index	Banking	Insurance	Consumer Goods	Oil and Gas	NGX 30
2015-01-04	30143.02	304.73	145.99	800.08	356.47	1360.44
2015-01-11	29032.29	286.21	139.87	770.51	362.14	1305.07
2015-01-18	29812.05	307.02	144.53	785.63	357.22	1347.79
2015-01-25	29562.07	297.93	141.60	781.84	357.07	1334.09
2015-02-01	29985.08	305.86	141.57	784.08	356.61	1349.66
2015-02-08	27585.26	278.52	138.74	721.36	357.96	1238.93
2015-02-15	29383.93	310.09	137.94	751.74	383.63	1328.41
2015-02-22	30103.81	327.72	141.75	769.36	386.09	1370.21
2015-03-01	31049.37	359.80	141.58	783.93	378.36	1425.74
2015-03-08	30719.36	359.61	142.43	767.29	364.74	1405.99
2015-03-15	29334.23	317.27	142.07	746.80	346.21	1327.57
2015-03-22	30562.93	342.29	143.46	777.06	372.97	1396.64
2015-03-29	35728.12	424.33	148.42	894.74	434.20	1646.78
2015-04-05	34930.02	397.84	145.47	904.05	407.60	1605.16
2015-04-12	35005.42	403.74	146.05	892.55	413.57	1607.58
2015-04-19	34485.72	396.08	149.79	874.92	410.45	1585.47
2015-04-26	34708.11	389.37	146.29	880.62	382.24	1588.06
2015-05-03	34388.12	397.25	147.12	858.42	379.47	1579.54
2015-05-10	34439.52	396.51	146.91	864.08	381.84	1583.59
2015-05-17	34272.09	395.86	148.37	853.78	374.48	1573.06
2022-06-26	51829.67	399.22	180.52	623.95	543.19	1888.50
2022-07-03	51557.41	397.99	175.96	615.08	540.95	1878.56
2022-07-10	52215.12	395.91	172.63	613.26	541.08	1895.62
2022-07-17	51979.92	379.85	175.75	601.18	561.63	1885.02
2022-07-24	50370.25	378.21	167.04	573.27	556.28	1820.25
2022-07-31	50722.33	388.17	166.43	590.49	559.60	1828.66
2022-08-07	49664.07	384.71	176.42	608.19	557.53	1775.29
2022-08-14	49370.62	387.22	173.95	601.91	552.68	1763.87
2022-08-21	49682.15	384.55	180.70	591.51	530.15	1772.42
2022-08-28	50045.83	389.22	180.79	603.38	533.59	1784.67
2022-09-04	49695.12	386.88	182.67	607.70	533.01	1772.48
2022-09-11	49475.42	374.09	177.96	606.05	532.15	1763.67
2022-09-18	49026.62	382.59	174.26	605.09	507.25	1746.22
2022-09-25	49024.16	379.20	168.60	584.68	508.26	1746.95
2022-10-02	47351.43	366.42	166.64	581.43	503.10	1686.69
2022-10-09	47569.04	373.48	169.51	577.12	492.37	1697.69
2022-10-16	44396.73	377.79	163.20	572.02	485.21	1601.22
2022-10-23	43912.64	378.05	159.32	569.98	484.03	1582.29
2022-10-30	44269.18	370.98	157.17	556.73	458.04	1600.44

Table 3. Weekly returns of All Share Index and some sector indexes (of the Nigeria Exchange (NGX) with a Binary Variable Created from NGX All Share Index Returns

Date	All Share Index	Banking	Insurance	Consumer Goods	Oil and Gas	NGX 30	Direction (Y)
2015-01-18	0.03	-0.06	-0.04	-0.04	0.02	-0.04	1
2015-01-25	-0.01	0.07	0.03	0.02	-0.01	0.03	0
2015-02-01	0.01	-0.03	-0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.01	1
2015-02-08	-0.08	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0
2015-02-15	0.06	-0.09	-0.02	-0.08	0.00	-0.09	1
2015-02-22	0.02	0.11	-0.01	0.04	0.07	0.07	0
2015-03-01	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.03	1
2015-03-08	-0.01	0.09	0.00	0.02	-0.02	0.04	0
2015-03-15	-0.05	0.00	0.01	-0.02	-0.04	-0.01	0
2015-03-22	0.04	-0.13	0.00	-0.03	-0.05	-0.06	1
2015-03-29	0.16	0.08	0.01	0.04	0.07	0.05	1
2015-04-05	-0.02	0.21	0.03	0.14	0.15	0.16	0
2015-04-12	0.00	-0.06	-0.02	0.01	-0.06	-0.03	1
2015-04-19	-0.01	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.00	0
2015-04-26	0.01	-0.02	0.03	-0.02	-0.01	-0.01	1
2015-05-03	-0.01	-0.02	-0.02	0.01	-0.07	0.00	0
2015-05-10	0.00	0.02	0.01	-0.03	-0.01	-0.01	1
2015-05-17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0
2022-06-19	0.00	-0.05	-0.01	-0.01	-0.02	-0.03	1
2022-06-26	0.00	0.00	-0.01	-0.02	0.00	0.00	1
2022-07-03	-0.01	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.01	0
2022-07-10	0.01	0.00	-0.03	-0.01	0.00	-0.01	1
2022-07-17	0.00	-0.01	-0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0
2022-07-24	-0.03	-0.04	0.02	-0.02	0.04	-0.01	0
2022-07-31	0.01	0.00	-0.05	-0.05	-0.01	-0.03	1
2022-08-07	-0.02	0.03	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0
2022-08-14	-0.01	-0.01	0.06	0.03	0.00	-0.03	1
2022-08-21	0.01	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	1
2022-08-28	0.01	-0.01	0.04	-0.02	-0.04	0.00	1
2022-09-04	-0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0
2022-09-11	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	-0.01	1
2022-09-18	-0.01	-0.03	-0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2022-09-25	0.00	0.02	-0.02	0.00	-0.05	-0.01	1
2022-10-02	-0.03	-0.01	-0.03	-0.03	0.00	0.00	0
2022-10-09	0.00	-0.03	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.04	1
2022-10-16	-0.07	0.02	0.02	-0.01	-0.02	0.01	0
2022-10-23	-0.01	0.01	-0.04	-0.01	-0.01	-0.06	1
2022-10-30	0.01	0.00	-0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.01	1